

Comparative Typology of English Uzbek Word Formations: A Discourse Analysis

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to explore how a new word is originated in English and Uzbek languages from the usage of word formation processes. Through a detailed inspection, this research highlights the unique aspects of word formations, how they are formed and modified, their differences and similarities and their stylistic usage in both languages and their implications for discourse examination.

Keywords: Word formation, Affixation, Compounding, Conversion, Borrowings, Backformation and A discourse analysis.

INTRODUCTION. Human have been utilizing the language for centuries to express their ideas, opinions and emotions with the help of forming words that fulfills the sentence structure completely. Word formation is a crucial aspect of a language structure which plays a significant role in interacting with individuals in a particular language. English is a West Germanic language spoken originally in England, and is now the most widely used language in the world. It is spoken as a first language by a majority of the inhabitants of several nations, including the United Kingdom, the United States, Canada, Australia, Ireland and New Zealand. It is the third most commonly spoken language in the world[2]. According to the investigations, in the second half of the twentieth century European languages have notably expanded their vocabulary. Furthermore, the New York Times reported that from 15 to 20 thousand lexical units grows year-by-year in the modern English language dictionary[1]. By moving to the Uzbek language, it is considered as a turkic language with its own distinct word formations. When creating a new word , affixation utilizes in both languages, however English tends to rely on compounding and blending, while Uzbek featured in agglutinative nature. In discourse analysis, we define English and Uzbek word formation processes' impact on overall structure and meaning of texts.

Affixation.

This type of word formation considered one of the best features in creating a wide variety of new words with with specific meanings.

English:

- English uses a wide range of prefixes and suffixes to create new words and reform existing ones.

For example: "Im-" (prefix) + " perfect " (a root) + "-ion" (suffix)= Imperfection

"Un-" (prefix) + " predict " (a root) + "-able" (suffix)= Unpredictable

Uzbek:

- Uzbek characterized as an agglutinative language. The agglutinative languages have words containing several morphemes that are always clearly differentiable from one another in that each morpheme represents only one grammatical meaning and the boundaries between those morphemes are easily demarcated; That is, the bound morphemes are affixes, and they may be individually identified[5].

For example: "Qo'shiq" (song) + "-chi" (suffix pointing to a person associated with songs)= "Qo'shiqchi" (a singer)

"O'yin" (play) + "-chi" (suffix pointing to a person associated with plays)= "O'yinchi" (a player)

Compounding.

Thus type of word modification process plays a considerable role in English language, as native and non-native speakers utilize it on their daily basis. Compounds are independent in form class ('part of speech') of the new word, the number of elements involved, whether they are written as one or two words or whether they are hyphenated and so on[6].

English:

- It is formed by combining two or more words into one , to create a specific term, with a few parts of speech.

For example: **Noun + Noun Verb + Noun**

Seafood = (Sea + Food) Playground = (Play + Ground)

Headmaster = (Head + Master) Swimming pool = (Swimming + Pool)

Adjective + Noun Adjective + Adjective

Sweet tooth = (Sweet + Tooth) Fat – free = (Fat + Free)

Whitehouse = (White + House) Bitter-sweet = (Bitter + Sweet)

Noun + Verb

Skincare = (Skin + Care)

Haircut = (Hair + Cut)

Uzbek:

- Compounding aids to broaden and clarify the meaning of the sentence in Uzbek language as well, and there are similarities in structuring words like the English lexicon.

For example: **Noun + Noun**

Oshxona = (Osh + Xona) – “Kitchen” (Palov(uzbek traditional food) + Room)

Kino yulduz = (Kino + Yulduz) –“Film star” (Film + Star)

Adjective + Noun

Sariq bola = (Sariq + Bola) – “Yellow boy(a boy who has a white skin texture or blonde)” (Yellow + Boy)

Oqsoqol = (Oq + Soqol) – “Elder” (White + Beard)

Noun + Verb

Mehnatsevar = (Mehnat + Sevar) – “Hardworking” (Work + Lover)

Suvko'taruvchi = (Suv + Ko'tauvchi) –“Water lifter” (Water + Lifter)

Verb + Noun

Ishjoy = (Ish + Joy) –“Working place” (Work + Place)

Yozuv mashinka = (Yozuv + Mashinka) –“Typewriter” (Writing + Machine)

Adjective + Adjective

To'qizil = (To'q + Qizil) –“Dark red” (Dark + Red)

Conversion:

Conversion is a characteristic feature of the English word-building system. It is also called affixless derivation or zero-suffixation.

English:

➤ In English a noun converts to a verb without changing letters.

“A cook” - Noun

“To cook” – Verb

For instance: My friend works in a foreign country as **a cook**.

My father **cooked** a dinner yesterday.

Uzbek:

➤ Uzbek with its Turkic roots relies agglutination to create new words.

Root word: “O'qimoq” (to read)

Affixes: “-it-“ (imperative mood)

“-moq” (infinitive suffix)

“-chi” (suffix which expresses desire)

“-lar” (polite version ending)

For instance: Otam meni Cambridge universitetda **o'qitmoqchilar**.

My father wants to educate me in the Cambridge university.

Borrowings:

Borrowing type of word formation defines as taking terms from other countries languages, and utilizing them, as it simplifies the communication between people around the world.

English:

- Despite, English being the most utilized language in all over the world, the English has many borrowed words. English is basically a Germanic language by structure. English vocabulary, however, comes from everywhere. Here is a brief summary of where many borrowed words in English come from: Latin–29%, French–29%, Greek–6%, other languages–6%, and proper names–4%. That leaves only 26% of English words that are actually English! Research date: December 24, 2018. By Misty Davidson.

For example: The words: Ketchup – originated in China

Spaghetti – originated in Italy

Café – originated in France

Uzbek:

- Uzbek belongs to the çagatay branch of the Turkic languages. The lexicon contains many words borrowed from Arabic, Persian and Russian due to Islamization and long-standing historical relationships.

For example: “Sabr” – (Patience) – Arabic word,

“Andisha” –(Wise) – Persian word

“Oltin” –(Gold) – Turkic word

Backformation:

Back-formation is one of the word-formation processes that is generally considered to be on the lower level. Back-derivation, retrograde-derivation, and deaffixation are a few additional names for this process[7]. In order to understand the back-formation process, it is important to have a clear understanding of the terms affix, suffix, and prefix. Backformation primarily forms new words by removing affixes from an existing word.

English:

- For example, if the suffix "-er" is added to the word "teach," the noun "teacher" is created. In back-formation, the reverse process is applied to existing words in order to create a new word. For example, if the suffix "-er" is removed from the word "teacher," the verb "teach" is created.

Back-formation can also be used to convert existing nouns into verbs. A classic example of this is the word "edit," which was derived from the noun "editor." Similarly, one could take the words "burglar" and "occupant" and create their respective verb forms: "burgle" and "occupy."

Uzbek:

- In Uzbek Backformation is less common, however it can be identified in words

For example: “Uyquchi” –(sleeper) -> “-chi”(suffix) removed

“Uyqu” –(Sleep) the noun hasn’t modified, but the meaning did.

“O’quvchi” –(student/reader) -> becomes “O’qi” –(Read)

A discourse analysis:

Discourse analysis plays a crucial role in comparative typology of English and Uzbek languages. The term 'discourse analysis' has come to be used with a wide range of meanings which cover a wide range of activities. As sociolinguists are particularly concerned with the structure of social interaction manifested in conversation, and their descriptions emphasise features of social context which are particularly amenable to sociological classification[8]. As for an example, the discourse analysis in contextual understanding helps in understanding patterns and variations in both languages. Pragmatic functions, clarifies how implications, speech acts and deixis are used in a

language. With those parts of elements it will be more comprehensible how speakers of English and Uzbek accomplish various interactive goals.

CONCLUSION.

Understanding the word formation, and how its structures can definitely provide an opportunity to be able to communicate properly, with diverse vocabulary range. Besides, by conducting discourse analysis we can deeply comprehend the word formation processes shape in communication patterns in both English and Uzbek languages. Studying these linguistic differences can improve cross-cultural interaction and promote language diversity awareness.

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